

COMPETITIVE POSITIONING AND STRATEGY OF THE ENTERPRISE AS KEY ELEMENTS OF COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE

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ABSTRACT. *To remain stable on the market companies must position themselves in such a way as to gain a competitive advantage over other market participants in the given industry. Taking into account competitive factors and developing a proper strategy for the enterprise determine its competitive advantage and help its successful performance on the market.*

The main goal of the present study is to trace the proportional relationship between positioning, strategy and enterprise advantage. The main expected results are to illustrate the fact that with proper positioning and strategy the enterprise increases its competitive advantage.

The main research methods used in the study are method of comparison, content analysis, method of analysis and synthesis, intuitive and systematic approach.

KEYWORDS: *competitiveness, competitive positioning, competitive strategy, competitive advantage, enterprise*

JEL Codes: *M11*

Introduction

The topic of competition and competitiveness has been valid for centuries and remains so today. Nowadays, it is becoming increasingly relevant given that we live in times of fierce competition, whether on an international, regional, corporate, or personal basis. The pursuit of competitive advantage, both at the macro and microeconomic levels.

Adam Smith believes that if there are no competitive advantages and no barriers to entry in a given industry, access to a given market will become easier, thereby intensifying competition in the industry. (Smith, A., 2010, p. 91). Traycho Spasov writes about competition that, in general terms, competition is a process, a procedure of purposeful, proactive creation and use of certain competitive advantages to conquer broader market territories and maximize the results of the economic process (Spasov, Tr., 2006, p. 131). In order to remain stable on the market, companies must position themselves in such a way as to gain a competitive advantage over other market participants in the industry. M. Porter argues that in order to achieve competitive success, companies in the country must have a competitive advantage in the form of either lower costs or differentiated products that command high prices. (Porter, M., 2001, p. 23. Proper positioning and striving for improvement, along with gaining a greater competitive advantage over competitors, is essential because if a company lags behind its competitors in terms of labour productivity, it will start to lay off staff: if its products are inferior and more expensive than those of its competitors, it will gradually go bankrupt (Marinov G., Ml. Velev, Ot., Gerasimova, 2001, p. 143). Competitive positioning should be understood as the place that a given business occupies among its immediate competitors, as well as the maintenance of acceptable positions or the acquisition of new ones in the process of comparing its actions with those of its competitors. Market share, measured by the share of sales of homogeneous goods at comparable prices, is of key importance for its assessment (Nenov, T., I., Minkov, 2015, p. 143). According to Philip Kotler, positioning means shaping the company's offer and image in such a way that the target market understands and appreciates the company's place relative to its competitors. The positioning of the company must be based on an

understanding of how the target market determines value and makes its choice among sellers. The tasks of positioning are carried out in three stages. First, the company must identify the possible distinctive features of its products, services, staff, and image that could set it apart from its competitors. Second, the company must establish criteria for selecting the most significant features. Third, the company must effectively signal to the target market how it differs from the competition. Then the company's product positioning strategy will prompt it to take the next step, namely, to plan its competitive marketing strategies (Kotler, P., 1996, p. 383). P. Kotler assumes that competitive advantage is an advantage over competitors, achieved on the basis of offering greater value or lower prices, or through more benefits that justify higher prices (Kotler P., 1996, p. 431). M. Porter writes that industry is an arena in which competitive advantage is won or lost. Through their competitive strategies, companies seek to define and establish an approach to competition in their industry that is both profitable and sustainable (Porter, M., 2004, p. 58). According to Vyara Kyurova, competitive advantage is a specific positive quality that distinguishes a given entity from its competitors (Kyurova, V., 2011, p. 79). In their quest to gain competitive advantage over their competitors, companies implement various strategies. These strategies inevitably lead to so-called "communication" between them, i.e., they take specific actions and behave in a certain way towards their competitors. Competitive action methods are a set of tools for rivalry between active entities in professional business (Nenov T., I., Minkov, 2015, p.142). The competitive behaviour of a given business entity is understood as the set of specific actions that the business entity undertakes in relation to its competitors in an effort to realize its business interests. It should be noted that these are not independent types of competitive actions, but an external manifestation of methods of competition (Nenov T., I., Minkov, 2015, p. 140). According to M. Kirova-Kicheva and S. Kirov the competence management is one of the main factors to develop a sustainable competitive advantage of the enterprise (M. Kirova-Kicheva, S. Kirov, 2021).

Based on the sources cited, we accept that the correct positioning of a company inevitably leads to its competitive advantage. By proper positioning, we mean the purposeful and detailed presentation of all distinctive features in the most appropriate way for a given situation, which would make the target audience (buyers, the public) prefer it over other competitors in the sector. We dare to say that by achieving this difficult task, the company already has a competitive advantage over its competitors, which it must strive not only to maintain, but also to increase continuously. For us, the competitive advantage of an enterprise is a set of benefits which, when applied in the best way to a given situation, will result in its superiority.

Taking competitive factors into account and developing the right strategy for a wine-producing enterprise determines its performance on the market. Operational efficiency means making the best possible use of the capacity of all of a company's production resources. Companies adapt to changing market conditions through their corporate strategy. In this way, the adaptability of the enterprise is a manifestation of its competitiveness, and corporate strategy is established as a cornerstone of this competitiveness (Dimitrova, R., 2018, p. 15). Philip Kotler is putting things this way. Companies should know five things about their competitors - who their competitors are, what their strategies are, what their goals are, what their strengths and weaknesses are, and what their response patterns are (Kotler, P., 1996, p. 273). Kotler concludes that a company's closest competitors are those that pursue the same target markets with the same strategy. A strategic group is a group of companies that follow the same strategy in a given target market (Kotler, P., 1996, p. 279). Furthermore, the company must constantly monitor the strategies of its competitors. Competitors have resources and revise their strategies over time. Companies must be alert to changes in customer desires and competitors' strategies to satisfy them (Kotler, P., 1996, p.

281). In addition to identifying competitors and studying their strategies, goals are the next important element that companies need to know about their competitors. According to P. Kotler, a company must know its competitor's goals in order to anticipate future moves and reactions. Knowing the strengths and weaknesses of a competitor allows a company to adjust its strategy and take advantage of the competitor's limitations, while avoiding areas where the competitor is strong. Knowing the typical response pattern of competitors helps companies select and coordinate their moves in a timely manner (Kotler, P., 1996, p. 295).

We accept that a competitive strategy is the path that a company must follow in order to compete with its rivals in the industry. This strategy must be carefully calculated, taking into account all the information available to the company at the time of its determination. It must predetermine (guarantee) the achievement of the company's goals, regardless of the constant internal and external influences of all objective and subjective factors, and it must also be adequate to respond to all challenges from competitors in the industry.

There is a close interconnection and interdependence between competitive advantages and competitive strategies. The successful functioning and development of a company in competitive markets requires it to have competitive advantages over its competitors. (Dimitrova, R., 2018, p. 37). The development and implementation of competitive strategies should lead to an increase in the level of competitiveness of the enterprise. In principle, various types of competitive strategies are considered and used in literature and practice:

- strategies for achieving competitive advantages;
- strategies for the company's behaviour in competitive struggle;
- strategies determined by the competitive status of the company (Dimitrova, R., 2018, p. 139).

Assuming that the competitiveness of an enterprise leads to its competitive advantages, we can assume that its competitive advantages also lead to the competitiveness of the enterprise. In this regard, we can assume that the factors for forming competitive advantages are precisely those that form the competitiveness of the enterprise. In order for the competitive advantage of the enterprise, once achieved, to be stable, and to be maintained and increased over competitors in the industry, attention must be paid to competitiveness. It is competitiveness that distinguishes economic entities in the industry from one another. An enterprise that outperforms its competitors is more competitive.

Based on our analysis of the sources, we assume that it is not only competitiveness that leads to competitive advantage, but also vice versa, i.e. competitive advantage leads to competitiveness. Competitive advantage leads to competitiveness, and competitiveness in turn leads to new competitive advantages.

Conclusion

Analysing the written above in this study, we can draw the following important conclusions;

1. The correct positioning of the enterprise inevitably leads to its competitive advantage.
2. The competitive strategy of the enterprise is the path that the enterprise must follow in the competitive struggle with competitors in the industry.
3. The competitiveness of the enterprise leads to its competitive advantages, therefore we can assume that its competitive advantages also lead to the competitiveness of the enterprise.

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